

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE CONCEPTS OF "QUALITY" AND "MANAGEMENT" IN THE EFFECTIVE MANAGEMENT OF THE QUALITY OF TRAINING

O'tasheva Lola Shoturayeva

Teacher of Termiz State Pedagogical Institute

Abstract: This article is written about the importance of the concepts of "quality" and "management" in the quality management of the modern education system, in which the views of various scientists are systematically analyzed.

Key words: quality, management, educational system, control, process, education and upbringing.

Modern education requires strict control and fair management. Ensuring the harmony of control and management in education is the key to quality and efficiency. If the quality of education is not systematically controlled in the educational system of Uzbekistan, certain problems arise in the educational process. Therefore, educational management should take into account the educational process, the type of education, its capabilities, and thereby ensure the effective operation of quality management. The change in the effectiveness and quality of management in education is related to the correctly selected management model and the practice of its consistent application in the continuous education system. After all, "The success of the reforms, our country's taking a worthy place among the developed and modern countries of the world, is inextricably linked with the development of science and education, and our ability to compete in this regard on a global scale. It also emphasizes the impact of education on social development. shows.

The State Inspection of Education Quality Control under the Cabinet of Ministers is the body that controls and coordinates the education system in Uzbekistan. Its activities are regulated by the decree of the President of the Republic

of Uzbekistan "On improving the activities of the State Inspectorate for Quality Control of Education under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan." In addition, each educational institution is governed and regulated by the Education Act and other regulations, as well as by its own governing board. At the meeting held on the 17th of 2018, the head of state said, "The quality of general secondary education should be raised to a new level. State educational standards and curricula should be revised based on what children need to know in each grade. It is necessary to create and publish textbooks based on the most modern methods, to strengthen the directions of technology, engineering sciences, mathematics, art, and foreign languages in schools, and to re-equip laboratories in this regard. They emphasized that it is necessary to pay attention to the integration with preschool education and higher education systems.

One of the main priorities of the state education is to ensure that education, including preschool education, is brought up to the modern level in the process of the policy of transition to an open, innovative society. The urgency of the problem of the quality of education in preschool educational institutions is increasing day by day. The most difficult task before the employees of the preschool educational institution is to ensure the unique memories of childhood while organizing education and upbringing in accordance with the requirements of the society. Today, every preschool educational institution must constantly prove its status with the high quality of education and upbringing process, modern scientific approaches and created conditions.

Activities of pre-school educational institutions are significantly different from other educational institutions due to the processes of children's age. Based on this, it is impossible to transfer the general theoretical positions of quality management directly to preschool education. Activities of pre-school educational institutions should be supplemented with new content in accordance with the characteristics. Researchers and other scientists of our republic conducted many researches on quality management in preschool educational institutions (R. Ahliddinov, R.

Zorayev, U. Inoyatov, P. Inisimov, M. M. Potashnik, T. P. Tratyakov, L. V. Pozdnyak, L.M. Chumichova) all of them developed their own technologies for improving the educational quality management system.

First of all, the purpose of the concept of "quality" in education is the ability to present the needs of the educational process to consumers through various innovative capabilities. The concept of "management" in education was defined by P.I. Raizes Tretyakov to the level of art. According to him, management processes in preschool educational institutions are based on objective laws, a specific educational system of education, a set of requirements for experience, principles, methods, tools and forms of social management, including education itself. based on the specific process.

The concept of "quality" as a basis of management in the preschool education system is multifaceted and is interpreted in its own way from the point of view of each participant. For children, it is learning in the form of fun games. And for parents

- exercise without fatigue
- maintaining the mental and physical health of their children
- conducting successful training
- supporting children's desire to learn
- ensure the possibility of admission to a prestigious school
- an institution for teaching prestigious subjects (foreign language, rhythmic gymnastics, mental exercises, etc.).

In a word, it is an effective place of education that prepares its children well through state programs before school.

For pedagogues, this means, firstly, the positive assessment of their work by the head of the preschool educational institution and parents, and secondly:

- successful implementation of educational programs with all pupils
- choosing optimal methods of working with children
- maintaining children's interest in the educational process
- monitoring the successful development of children in the educational process

- maintenance of children's physical and mental health;
- it is important to provide all the necessary equipment and tools while using the working time wisely in the educational process.

Therefore, the concept of quality in preschool education management is the ability to properly design services to meet the educational and educational needs of consumers. It is important that the control and management system in education is organized in a professional, open, transparent and fair manner, with logical consistency. Therefore, how well the work is carried out in the educational institution, the correct choice of the management model, and the fair organization of educational quality control have a strong impact on educational efficiency. . Today, a distinctive feature of the management of the quality of education in a preschool educational institution is the correct development of innovative approaches aimed at the spiritual development of students, as well as their spiritual and educational development. is to increase the capacity. For this, educators need to be professionally competent and use all the knowledge, skills and abilities they have acquired along the way.

In conclusion, it can be said that today, based on the priorities of the socio-economic development of our country, it is necessary to fundamentally improve the education system, fundamentally revise the personnel training system, and create opportunities for education at the level of international standards. is being implemented. Therefore, in order to ensure the quality of education and introduce it into the national education system, it is one of the urgent tasks to study the organizational and pedagogical features of improving the control and management structures of advanced foreign countries.

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